

EFFECT OF FLOODING IN LOKOJA URBAN ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses attention on the hazard of flooding, which have become a menace in recent times. The effect of which are huge losses recorded in life and property. Urban areas which are expected to be safer are not spared of this menace. The occurrence of the flooding is as a result of bad planning and bad choice of settlement sites. Poverty owes its own expression in dictating to people where they should settle. Lokoja township which is the area of study, also show that there is poor attitude to management of the environment in terms of refuse disposal and the erection of structures in areas of high risk. The heavy rainfall in the months of July, August and September is another major factor. Flood waters often jump artificial drains which were inadequate in some cases, the drafts silt up. It is suggested that there should be a well articulated and comprehensive physical planning and land use planning control.

KEYWORDS: Rainfall, planning, urban areas, high risk, environment

INTRODUCTION

Flood occurs when more rainfalls than the soil and vegetation can absorb. The excess water runs off the land in greater quantities than rivers, streams, ponds and wet lands can contain. Such heavy rains, periodically cause rivers to overflow their banks, spilling onto the surrounding floodplains. In an urbanizing environment, the infiltration capacity is further reduced by the replacement of ground cover with impervious urban surfaces. Under such conditions, surface overland flow becomes the dominant method of disposal of excess rainwater. The term urban flood can be defined as any overland flow over urban streets sufficient to causes significant property damage, traffic obstructions, nuisance and health hazards. It includes river flood, flash floods and flood pondages (Rashedd, 2008).

Across the globe, studies show that more than two billion people representing one-third of the world's population have been subjected to natural disasters in the last decade, with floods and droughts accounting for 86 percent of all such catastrophes. The studies indicate that although earthquakes, volcanic eruptions and landslides may be more dramatic, and take a very high toll on human lives.

Floods have longer lasting and more far-reaching effects on the health of ordinary people (world socialist web site, WSWS, 5 October, 20002). It is common in flood plains, along longer rivers and coastal areas. If such area are not settled by man, the went attracts little or no attention, but when such areas are settled with large population such as the Ganges, Nile, Mississippi, Hwang Ho and Niger Benue flood plains, flooding becomes a menace causing great disaster to lives and properties (Giwa, 2006).

WSWS reported on April 2000 that south East Africa experienced the heaviest rain storms in 50 years as a result of three weeks of downpours. The floods that swept through the neighboring countries of South Africa, Botswana and Zimbabwe hard particularly hit Mozambique some places experience a whole years rainfall in just three days. Mozambique was effectively cut to two by the flood water north of the capital Maputo. The river valleys of the Limpopo, the Elephant river and save river broke their banks and flooded enormous tract of land.

On 8 August 2005, heavy rains that lasted for non hours caused flood with unusual heavy currents in Jallingo, the state capital of Taraba. A bridge collapsed when the Jallingo River burst its banks as a result of the heavy down pour. 60,000 people were displaced from the homes and over 200 people died as a result of the floods. The flooding was said to be unprecedented in the last 30 years. It cleaved away major bridges and road networks linking the city with other parts of the country (International Federation Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, 14 March, 2007). Similarly, at least 24 persons were confirmed dead in Song Local

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Government Area of Adamawa State, as flash flood left at least three Local Government Areas devastated following two day of torrential rainfall. The flood which affected Yola North and South and Song Local Government, left hundreds of building and hectares of farmland submerged, while the song Galamayo bridge was washed away (This Day, 7 August, 2007).

Severe flooding has become an almost annual occurrence in Nigeria especially in the northern part of Nigeria. In 1989, flooding in Kano State resulted in the loss of 142 lives, destruction of 160,000 housed, washing away of 12,000 farms, displacement of 180,000 people and damage of residences and infrastructure worth about 520 million naira (NEST, 1991). In 1999, 38 people lost their lives and more than 200,000 people were displaced in the worst flood in 40 years in Niger State (BBC News, October 6, 1999). In 2000, twenty people died and 48,000 displaced after floods hit the state of Kano.

In Jigawa, 180 deaths were registered, 700 people injured and 35,000 displaced (WSWS, 5 October, 2001). In September 2003, property worth millions of naira were lost as a result of a heavy downpour which swelled the waters of river kaduna. The most affected areas are settlements that have located close to the banks of the river (Adejo, 2003).

Urban development process giver rise to increase runoff generation in response to removal of vegetation and concomitant increase in soil compaction and poor planning which invariably encouraged erosion and flooding phenomenon (Slay Maker, 2001). Lokoja town has experienced a number of flood disaster in the past years, (1932, 1965, 1980, 2012). In October, 2012 flood disasters were recorded in Lokoja and its environment as a result of the swelling of River Niger and Benue due to up stream discharge of rivers beyond the Nigeria boarder and heavy rainfall. The effects are the displacement of people and destruction of property worth millions of naira.

The intensity of flood problems over time and space in Nigeria Urban centres is closely related to the rapid rate of urban expansion, especially where the simultaneous provisions for an adequate urban runoff disposal system is lacking as it is in most Nigeria cities (Onoker horaye, 1995). The risk of flooding is derived as a function of both the probability of a flood happening and its impact. In urban areas, the impact can be very high because the areas affected are mostly built up area and contain vital infrastructure (post, 2007).

Many floods events in Lokoja have cause little damage and usually soon forgotten, except by those most directly affected, the floods of October, 2012 due to the swelling of River Niger and Benue, resulted in major disasters. The flood event of last year alone resulted in erosion damage, destruction of socio-economic activities, displacement of thousands of people, and damage of residences and infrastructure worth millions of naira (oral interviews, 2012). This calls for a study of the underlying causes of flood in Lokoja town.

THE STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in Lokoja town, the state capital of Kogi State and the headquarters of Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State (Fig 1)

MAP OF KOGI STATE SHOWING THE STUDY AREA

The geology consists of under laid Precambrian rocks of the basement complex which are mainly granite, gneiss and quartzite. These rocks have had a complex history involving several phase of orogenesis and subsequent regional uplift and depression. These movements have determined the main pattern of drainage and the regional pattern of erosion and sedimentation since early cretaceous time (Ologe, 1995).

Climatically, the duration, intensity and the spatial spread of rainfall in Lokoja is generally controlled by the intertropical discontinuity (ITD). The rainy season begins when the ITD is north of the study area. The main monthly temperature rainfall is about 1680mm, while the main monthly temperature is 32c⁰. The relative humidity is about 58%.

The vegetation falls within the Guinea Savanna of the middle belt with tall grasses and trees of different kinds, while the soil is the tropical ferruginous mostly formed on granite and gneiss parell materials (Abaje, 2007).

The town (Lokoja) has witnessed a tremendous growth in population and area coverage during the last 22yrs. The built-up areas have expanded within the same period in an attempt by individuals, groups and government to meet the increasing demands for residential houses, roads, markets, parks and institutional facilities. The development of these urban facilities involves the replacement of the vegetation cover with impervious urban land use surfaces which increases surface run off.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Climatic data were collected from the Hydrology section of the Kogi State Water Board Investigation Department, Lokoja. These were used in calculating the mean annual and monthly rainfall, mean monthly temperature and relative humidity of the study area.

A steel tape was used to make direct measurement of the residential houses from the River Niger Bank. Measurement of the river to the build-up area were also taken. From the Muritala Bridge down stream, 70 houses along the river down to Ganaja Village were selected through systematic sampling. Flood affected persons and others residing close to the flood prone areas were randomly sampled to obtain information about their perceptual assessment of the intensity, causes and damage from the flood of October, 2012. During and after rainstorms, the researcher drove along the flood plain and major roads and streets in order to make proper observations and report appropriately what was witnessed from the field.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

TABLE 1: YEARLY DISCHARGE RECORD OF NIGER RIVER AND RAINFALL.

Year	Rainfall (mm)	Minimum discharge	Maximum discharge	Range	Mean water level
2008	25	3628	17713	14085	8.8
2009	22	2811	19914	13103	9.4
2010	100	2700	15548	12848	8.2
2011	130	2664	23491	20827	10.5
2012	140	3756	24486	21836	10.63

Source: Extracted from NIWA gange record in Lokoja.

Table I above shows the mean rainfall in the town for the 2008-2012 periods. A close examination of the figure shows a peak range in the month of October, 2012. While the maximum discharge was in the month of October, 2012 resulted in high antecedent precipitation index (APT). The consequential effect due to the heavy rainfall was the flood hazard of that year. The result of direct field measurement of residential house from the Niger bank and of the river is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2: DISTANCE OF RESIDENTIAL HOUSES FROM RIVER BANK AND WIDTH.

Distance From River Bank	Width
7.80	5.65
0.27	5.40
1.40	5.40
1.54	5.40
9.40	4.60
2.24	4.60
1.65	4.30
1.73	5.30
1.74	5.30
10.44	3.40
Total = 38.21	Total = 49.35
Mean Distance= 3.82	Mean Width= 4.94

Source: field work, 2013

Volumetry Discharge of Niger River at Lokoja.

Field observations show that increasing frequency and severity of floods do not stem from, heavy rainfall alone. It is noted that increasing rate of urbanization in the absence of well articulated and comprehensive physical planning and land use planning control have caused the banks to be heavily settled. There are situations where buildings are at zero distance from the bank of the river. The further measured distance is 10.44 meters, where the surging waves of the flood did not spare, when it occurred recently. In some houses the flood water level reached between 0.30-0.72m downstream of the studied area.

There is visible evidence of the river expanding its channel width through lateral erosion around Pakta and Ganaja road; as a result, some residential houses have already been vacated before flooding. Where man has built hard concrete walk or floors, erosion under mines such efforts with a high vulnerability of a collapse in the near future. All these result from high and sudden urban storm runoff which forcefully releases its waters down the channel due to inadequate drainage facilities and dumping of refuse in drains and drainage paths. Impervious roads surface and built up surface also intercept rainfall which accumulates to form flood water.

Field observation shows that the river channel expansion is due to intensive farming enticed by the rich alluvial deposits and the constant tramping by human as path ways, domestic animals and especially pigs that often retire to the river in the hot afternoons. They often dig the mud and create caves which are easily, enlarged by wave action in the rainy season.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Flooding is a major environmental problem in Lokoja, Kogi State. It is not even more frequent but more severe and devastating in recent times especially the flood of October, 2012. The severity do not only result from heavy rainfall alone, but also increasing rate of urbanization without proper physical planning and land use planning control to cope with the development. Floods are therefore likely to increase in the study area if no changes are made to increase to the management of the River Niger that passes through the town (Lokoja). This can be a major source of water pollution.

Rather than accepting the flooding as an inevitable product of nature, however, the residents, political leaders, engineering and environmental specialists have to look into the human actions that causes the severity of the flood and what steps might be taken in the future to avoid or mitigate another such catastrophe.

It is suggested that land use planning should avoid developing and building on flood plains, and policy for handling problems of floods should also include discouraging land users from engaging in activities in flood prone areas that have great potentials for runoff through enforceable land use laws. Based on the findings in this study, the provision of adequate drainage facilities should be an important segment of all development planning programs in the study areas. It is also recommended that River channel should constantly be cleared of trash materials as accumulation of such could easily block passage of the water and hence result in severe cases of flooding. Runoff can also be checked by retention ponds and other creative means to avoid much overland flow of water. In order to combat flooding effectively in the study area, it is recommended that the physical and human determinants of flooding should be understand. This calls for environmental management and perception studies.

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